

Research

Export Potentiality of Flower Industry: A Case Study on Bangladeshi Flower Industry

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Abstract: Flower being introduced as a business item to the international market by Colombia, in the early eighteenth century, has attracted many other countries as a means of earning foreign currencies. Bangladesh flowers cultivation was commercially established in 1980' in Jhikargachar, a district of Jessore. Over the years, this business has taken a good shape in the domestic market. Europe and North America have been dominating the flower industry for many years but suddenly export of flowers has seen a decline in this region as the importers are moving toward lower-priced markets like Kenya, Ethiopia, Ecuador, China, Israel, Malaysia and India. Bangladesh has also experienced a drastic change in the flower cultivation. Flower cultivation is highly profitable compared to agricultural crops. The study reveals that because of natural advantages. Such as fertile soil, good climate conditions and other facilities, a bright prospect of flower business and floriculture which is the competitive advantage of Bangladesh. The study examined the export volume of flowers of Bangladesh and anticipated future export value. This paper also describes the latent aspects which can help Bangladesh controlling the global export market. The paper examined domestic markets and explained various factors that are hindering local production and marketing. By minimizing the complications Bangladesh can ensure uninterrupted production of flowers which can pave the way to export. This article starts with a clear focus on flower business, objectives of the study, scope, methodology. And the later sections cover with data analyses. Finally, the study has offered some possible arena where this research can be further expanded.

Keywords: Flower Industry, Export, Import, Export Potentiality , Floricultural Industry, Flower folia

Introduction

Flower business is the activities to create and increase the demand for the flower in the market. As the flower is the agricultural commodity and most of its production depends on nature. Flower business is spreading its fragrance far and wide whether in form of international Tulip or Orchids or national Roses or Lilies which available in the market. The flower is a horticulture product that is commonly loved by everyone having a minimum sense of pleasure and feeling (Hossain & Rahman,1994) by and large; love for flowers is ingrained in us. Flowers have been regarded as an embodiment of human taste and aesthetics. The floral industry is one of the major industries in many developing and underdeveloped countries. The flower farming is an important and profitable enterprise in the Agriculture sector of Bangladesh.

It was Columbia which first introduced flowers as a business item to the international market. The huge success of Columbia in selling flowers to the international market inspired others countries namely Netherlands, Columbia, Israel, Mexico, Peru, Kenya etc. involved in exporting flowers. In Bangladesh, the growth of commercial flower production can be traced the back to early 70s to mid-80s when large-scale commercial production started in Jikargacha upazila of Jessore district (Sultana, 2003). Later it speeded largely in Jessore, Savar, Chuandanga, Mymensingh , Gazipur, Narayngonj, Gopalganj . In recent years it seems that a revolution has taken place particularly in Dhaka citizen's attitude towards flowers (Shams,1999). At the primary stage, flowers were mainly used by human beings to provide interesting ornamental effects and its business was confined around the Hotels of the Capital and business cities of the World (Hossain & Rahman,1994).President of Bangladesh Flower Growers and Exporters Association (BFA) M Ahsan Ullah said currently the demand for Rose, Marigold, Gladiolus, Gerbera, Orchid, Lily, Tube Rose and some other flowers is increasing and apart from meeting local demand, flowers can be exported in large amounts if some steps are taken to maintain quality.

There are high demands of flowers in counters like USA, UK, Canada, France, Italy and Spain. The total world export of flowers during 2002-2003 exceeded to 1.37 billion dollars. According to the experts, the trade is growing at a highly encouraging rate of 11% percent a year. This has enabled countries like Columbia, Guatemala, Germany, Netherland, Kenya, India and some other Asian countries to think about the trade of flower as well (Ahmed, 1995). The typical Japanese consumer spends on average of \$50 a year on floral products. In Europe, the German consumer

spends over \$30 and even the British, who traditionally prefer to grow their own, doubled their spending on fresh flowers to \$25 in the last five years (Ahmed, 1995).

Bangladesh has the high potential to be leading as the top exporter in Asia (Shykh Seraj,2008)

It is a potential market to export to China. Bangladesh exported Cut flowers, worth \$.8 million, during July-November 2017 into a few destinations like Saudi Arab, Malaysia, Britain, and UAE. Bangladesh's stake in the global trade of flowers is negligible i.e. 0.3 percent. Nevertheless, it has good potential in the production of flowers due to the favourable atmosphere. This study attempts to find out the challenges, bars and difficulties in exporting flowers to the international market and ways to overcome those related problems.

Flower business is the most emerging sector currently in Bangladesh from the point of view of production, export and earning. This study is mainly focused on various actors related to the floral industry of Bangladesh from the production to export process. this study has tried to utilize the accumulated information from gathered from farmers, marketing agents, dealers and members of the export-import controller of Bangladesh. This report attempts to include random samples. This report will explore different data and analyse the export potentiality of flower business in the foreign market.

The aim of the study is to explain the factors influences the growth of flower export and the challenges it's been tangled in. The specific objectives of the study are given below

1. Current scenario of flower business in the world market
2. The current status of Flower business in Bangladesh
3. The overall status of supply chain and export of flower in Bangladesh
4. The major Challenges and opportunities

Literature Review

With increasing production of flower throughout the world, flower business is now being considered one of the largest industries in the world market. Continuous development of greenhouse technology and advantage in plant biotechnology, uninterrupted shipping, progressive marketing and selling approaches all together have made this floral industry lucrative and profitable. Flower industry has omnipresence in the both developed and developing

countries with annual global trade value of more than 100 Billion US dollar (Statistics Brain, 2017) According to the experts the trade is growing at a highly encouraging rate of 11 percent a year. For years Europe has been dominating the flower industry being the biggest flower export market of with 77% of the total market share. The Netherlands is the world's largest exporters and producer of flowers with a global market share of 52 %.

According to Worldatlas.com, The Netherlands yielded a revenue of 3.2 billion us dollar in 2016. Their major flower exporters include Italy, Denmark, Belgium, Germany, Spain, France and the UK (Institute of Business Research 1997). Africa and South America are now taking up more of flower export where in the South and North America regions, the US is the centre of flower business and consumption where US alone generated 5 million dollars in the year 2017 (CBI,2017). Besides the US, Canada, Mexico, Columbia and Ecuador are the main producers and exporters of flower (Xia, Deng, Zhou, Shima, & Silva, 2006)). In the last couple of decades, Africa is showing remarkable performance in flower production and export with Kenya is now the 2nd largest cut flower supplier to the European market and contributes 25% of total EU cut flower import Other mass African exporters of cut flowers are Zimbabwe, Tanzania, Uganda and Zambia (Semboja et al., 2000)

The flower industry is no longer in the hand of Europe-Africa region and the American Region Asian region has also been added to the list. The Asian flower industry is worth billions of dollars and China alone is valued at more than 11 billion dollars, according to China Horticulture Business Services (2017). Xia et al., (2006) stressed that Compared to Europe-Africa region and the American region, floriculture in most Asia-Pacific countries is still at a developing stage, due to lack of advanced technologies and newest plant varieties. While Zienkiewicz (2015) argued that Asian floriculture market is thriving and awaiting global interest. The production value in Asia was around €40 billion, has a 53% share of the world production (Zaman, 2013). Japan, Thailand, China, Taiwan and India are leading global producer and exporters of the flower. Unlike other regions, Asia mostly focuses on exporting the flowers.

Xia et al., (2006) studied that, the total consumption of world floriculture products was estimated at \$34.2 and \$36.3 billion in 1998 and 2002, respectively. The three most important floriculture consumption regions in 2002 were Europe (66.7%), the US (19.3%) and Japan (10.7%). If we look at floriculture consumption in 2002 from a country perspective, the US was the biggest consumer at \$6.99 billion, sharing 19.3% of the world total value. Germany was second largest

(18.8%), followed by Japan (10.7%), France (8.5%), United Kingdom (UK, 8.5%), Italy (6.8%), the Netherlands (4.1%), Spain (4.1%), Switzerland (2.6%), and Poland (2.6%). These ten countries shared 85% of the world total floriculture consumption.

Bangladesh holds a promising position in flower production and export although the quality is scant compared with other Asian countries. Bangladesh has been bestowed with fertile soil, auspicious weather that makes the flowers production favourable. A research paper on economic policy on WTO Agreement on agriculture by Choudhury and Sharifa (2005) discussed the potential of agro-processing products in Bangladesh. They have presented global economic situation, a review of business environment, investment, export and import climate of Bangladesh. They have also indicated trends of production and export of agricultural and agro-processed products from Bangladesh. They also have analysed the National Agricultural policy and Export Policy of Bangladesh, highlighting features of Agreement on Agriculture, and explained the agriculture trade under GATT regime. Statistics report from EPB Bangladesh exported flowers 42.89 million and 50.46 million us dollars in the fiscal year of 2010-2011 and 2011-2012 respectively. According to EPB export data, the country exported cut flowers and foliage worth \$ 16.58 million during July-November 2013, an amount that is 15.2% more than that of the export target.

According to Bangladesh Bureau of statistics (2013) the flower is growing by 10 percent every year. The current market size is Tk 10 billion and the flower is being cultivated in 2,500 acres of land across the country, particularly in Jhenidah, Savar, Tangail, Mymensingh, Gazipur, Narayanganj and Jessore reported by (Zaman,2013).Demand for flowers in Bangladesh grew as more and more people have been elevated to urban middle class (Mou,2012).Shiraj (2016)suggested that flower export target was fixed at Tk 110 crore in FY 2015-16 and already more than Tk 70 crore has been earned from July to December. Export of flowers and floral products has seen an impressive growth, contributing to the gross domestic product (GDP) as the entrepreneurs are trying to tap a strong demand for the non- conventional product in the global market said an EPB official. Bangladesh has a competitive advantage due to its favourable climatic and topography as well as low labour cost and relatively low capital investment which are aiding the industry to increase exports. (Khan, 2013). Regardless of all these growths in the international market, Bangladesh is failing to compete with the top exporter countries of flowers. local production has been unsuccessful in filling the home demand. To satisfy the market

demand, various flowers, such as chrysanthemum, tuberose, gladiolus have been imported from India and orchids, gerbera, anthurium and Thai rose from Thailand every year. Bangladesh has to spend Tk. 2-3 million in importing flowers and ornamental plants from abroad. (Mou,2012) . While Abedin (2014) argued that the demand for Cut flowers, worth about USD 8.0 million, in Bangladesh of which USD 5.0 million is locally produced and rest of the amount is imported mainly from China and Indonesia. Besides, Bangladesh imports a huge amount of artificial flowers per year to meet local demands. Artificial flowers are imported mainly from China and India.

Shykh Seraj (2008) suggested that flower export from Bangladesh has been indicating a positive growth for the past few years, the amount of global export has dropped in the last four years. This sudden slump is due to the inability of the farmers to cope up with local and international demand. According to financial express (2016), flower production between 2009 and 2016 has increased significantly with local consumption of flower increased substantially, hence farmers struggling to supply. Report from the export promotion bureau (2016) has shown that the country earned US\$ 1,530.22 from exports of cut flowers in the fiscal year 2015-2016, while the earnings were US \$ 25,516.07 in the FY (2012-2013) Last fiscal's exports also registered a 58.36 percent fall over that of the previous FY 2014-15.

Chowdhur and Khan (2015) considered a sharp rise in the demand for flowers in the domestic market is responsible for the lower-than-expected level of export. They suggested that the downward trend in a shipment of flowers is for the factors like inadequate airspace, lack of post-harvest management and cooling transportation facilities.

This study has been undertaken to determine, the actors and process related to flower production and export and the factors caused the sudden plummet in the export. This study has also tried to explore the flower industry and analyse the global export potentiality of the flower. Lastly, This study has scrutinised the supply chain of flower market and the opportunities, challenges and constraints in production and marketing of flower industry in Bangladesh (Abdin & Abdin, 2014)

Methodology

This research paper is based on both mixed research approach. Qualitative research refers to investigative research. It is used for understating the views and perception of a respondent over an issue. This research approach analyzes a problem from a deeper position while observing

thoughts and judgement of an individual on that. Whereas quantitative approach allows enumerating data which is later converted into statistics. For collecting logical information which is enabled to justify the objectives, this paper required both qualitative and quantitative research. This research paper has led to interview various respondents from different organizations, associations, shops and farmlands and collected data have been converted into comprehensible information that has been analyzed by qualitative approach. Again for the quantitative analysis appropriate numerical and statistical data have been gathered from different secondary sources which were used in quantitative analysis. And it is the nature of this research paper that compelled the author to apply both qualitative and quantitative approach.

This is a descriptive research where the data analysis has followed mixed approach. The data is collected from different sources have also been analysed and presented using statistical tools like graphs, charts and some statistical formulas related to trend analysis.

Data Analysis and Findings

The current status of Flower business in Bangladesh

In Bangladesh, flowers production dates back to 1980' when, for the first time, flowers had been stated cultivating in Jessore, Jhikargachha. There are more than 50 types of the flower being cultivated in different Zillas. Jessore, Shenandoah, Mahespur, Jibon-Nagar, Narayangaonj, Rajshahi, Maymansin, Rangpur, Pabna, Shirajganj, Munsiganj, Narshingdi, Sylhet, Dinajpur, Chattagram, feni and Noakhali are the principle district for flower production.

A good number of flower shops are also established in district towns. There are reportedly around 4000 retail shops of flowers in the country. Forty percent of the retail shops are located in Dhaka, while Chittagong and Sylhet having 25% each and the remaining 10% of the shops are in other district towns. At a wholesale flower market (in Dhaka), some 700 traders do flower business worth at least 2-5 lakhs every day. Only in Shahbag, there are 50 retail and 200 wholesale shops. Popular flowers: Orchid, Mum, Gerbera, Gladiolus, tuberose, Rose, Cherry, Lily and Marigold rose, tuberose, gladiolus, carnation, gerbera, gypsophila, limonium, anthurium, philodendron and daisy.

Prices of flower in the local market:

There has been a drastic sight in Bangladeshi culture. Buying behaviour has taken a good shape in the domestic market. Different special days have become a reason to spend money on like

valentines day, mother's day, international mother language day, pohela boishakh, pohela bosonto etc. But the price of flowers is very fluctuating, someday 200 stems of the rose amount for 200tk, another day it becomes 6000tk. People related to flowers business are hence uncertain about the demand for flowers and because of this anticipation is ambiguous.

Table 01: the Local price of selected flowers

Flower Name	Wholesale Price Per Stick (Tk)	Retail Price Per Stick (Tk)
Rose	2	5-8
Chrysanthemum	2	5-6
Gladiolus	12	15-18
MeriGold	10 (garland)	18-20
Gerbera	6	10-12

Source: Field survey (2018)

Although Bangladesh has been self-sufficient in producing flowers and fulfilling local demands with high-quality flowers since the last decades, import rate is still high. Retailers and wholesalers imports a large number of flowers especially rose, lily, orchid and chrysanthemum from India and China. In Bangladesh 2-3 million, US\$ is spent on importing flowers. Import accounts for more than 40% of the supply of flower to the local market.

Table 02: Comparison of local price of (Bangladesh vs Netherlands)

Flower Name	Netherlands Initial Market Price Average Price Per Stem (in BDT)	Bangladesh Initial Market Price Average Price Per Stem (in BDT)
Rose (Large)	35	4
Rose (small)	12.36	3
Gerbera (Large)	26.38	14
Gerbera (small)	20.40	8
Gladiolus (Big)	38	10

Source: Plasmeijer and Yanai (2009)

The buying pattern of consumers in the global market has seen changing since 2000, where top exporters like Netherlands, United Kingdom, Germany and United States are losing their dominating position. From many reasons causing this collapse, the price of the flowers can be considered one of the principle reasons. The high price offered by top exporting countries is making the wholesalers, retailers and end-customers move to markets offering lesser price for

flower import. Different countries are grabbing this opportunity and emerging as flourishing exporters. Even in Asia, there is a demand for flowers and only a few countries like India, China, Malaysia, Israel are filling that demand. Bangladesh produces flowers at a very cheap cost, and the soil, weather and other topology are supporting its flowers cultivation. In table 11, a price comparison has been presented as to evaluate the visible price difference between Netherland and Bangladesh. As the top exporter, Netherland is selling flowers at a very high price whereas in Bangladesh the price of flowers is very lower. Bangladesh could easily grab for being low-cost producers. Bangladesh can catch markets where demands are very high for flowers.

The overall status of supply chain and export of flower in Bangladesh

The supply chain of flower business in Bangladesh

The supply chain of flowers in Bangladesh is very complex in nature. There are various reasons for the complexity of slow and inefficient transportation, fluctuating demand and supply, slow communication among growers and wholesalers/retailers etc. This research has revealed different participants of the supply chain of flowers and they are farmers/growers, wholesalers, wholesalers cum retailers, farmers cum wholesalers, farmers cum wholesalers cum retailers, stockists and customers.

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Figure 01: Supply chain of Flowers in Bangladesh

Source: Author-Constructed

The Distribution channel of flower business in Bangladesh

In Bangladesh, 70%-80% of total commercial flowers are produced in Jessore (Godkhali , Jhikaracha). But despite all these factors, the centre of the distribution channel is still Dhaka. Later from Dhaka flower are bought by trader coming from different districts such as Rangpur, Dinajpur, Pabna, Shirajganj, Mymensing, Munsiganj, Narshingdi, Sylhet, Chattagram, Cumilla, Noakhali and Feni. Some trader of Dhaka sends different flowers to a different corner of the country only to promote flower cultivation.

Figure 1: Distribution Channel Of Flower

Source: Author Constructed

The overall status of export of flower in Bangladesh:

From 2003 Bangladesh started to export flowers. Initially, the destination had been confined to middle eastern counties (UAE, Saudi Arabia) but later the export was expanded to other Asian countries like China, Japan and, Vietnam. Later in 2010 export took place in Germany and Portugal. In table 10, the sketch of export is given where, it is visible that, Saudi Arabia and

UAE have always been a constant trading partner of Bangladesh. But after 2011 the export has taken a negative direction. Export to Saudi Arab and UAE has been sinking. However no new marketed has been penetrated lately yet old trading partners have lowered their purchase order from Bangladesh. But the prospects of flower export are still positive as Bangladesh is at budding stage of the floricultural industry, so it needed time to grow progressively. Other Asian countries such as India, China, Vietnam, m Japan, Hongkong, have made a place in the flower market as consumers have shifted toward the cheaper market. Bangladesh has the privilege of low labour cost, favourable climate, advantageous topology and fertile lands, Bangladesh can grab the opportunity to capture the global market.

Current export from Bangladesh

Fiscal year	Export value us (mill)	Growth
2004-2005	\$ 7.34	
2005-2006	\$ 21.07	187%
2006-2007	\$ 32.71	55%
2007-2008	\$ 55.98	71%
2008-2009	\$ 33.67	-40%
2009-2010	\$ 39.75	18%
2010-2011	\$ 42.89	8%
2011-2012	\$ 50.46	18%
2012-2013	\$ 41.41	-18%
2013-2014	\$ 39.28	-5%
2014-2015	\$ 11.36	-71%
2015-2016	\$ 4.73	-58%
2016-2017	\$ 0.80	-83%

Table 03: the Total export value of Flowers from Bangladesh

Source: Export Promotion Burea (2017)

The table has presented the current exporting volume of Bangladesh. Bangladesh has shown praiseworthy performance during FY (2010-2012) but there is a sudden drop in the export. This decline can occur due to various issues such as political turmoil, poor quality of flowers, no direct link to the foreign customers, lack of promotion and many more. This decline has been increasing from the FY (2013-2014) and still showing a negative impact. Fig 12 shows a declining rate of export from Bangladesh to the world market. From the year 2004 to 2011 the export market was satisfactory. In FY(2005-2006) 21.07 million US\$ earned by exporting flowers and for the next 5 years the export had been showing remarkable output. Bangladesh is a regular sending flower to Middleeastern counties (see Appendix 2). Other Asian countries even Neighbour nations like India, Srilanka, China is emerging as top flower exporting nation as customers are demanding cheaper flowers. However Bangladesh could not grab any opportunity.

Figure 2: Flower Export from Bangladesh (2004-2017)

Source: Author-Constructed

In FY (2011-2012) 41.41 million US\$ was earned and this has become the benchmark in the history of the export of the flower. But a sudden drop in export happened after that year in FY (2013-2014) when Bangladesh got 39.28 million US\$. In FY(2016-2017) the export has come to the lowest point wrong only .8 million US. The trendline the fight showing this diminishing behaviour of flower export. In FY (2005-2006) the growth rate of export was 187% which was undoubtedly unexpected achievement for Bangladesh. But the rate is heavily declining. The rate has never sown positive line after FY (2012-2013). The lowest rate is earned in FY (2017-2016) where the rate is -83 %. There can be many reasons for the plunge. Political turmoil, exchange

rate fluctuation, natural calamities are some of the factors that can be blamed. For the inconsistent trading, exporters do not dare enter into foreign trading. Bangladesh altogether could not promote its flower to the global market thus the buyers are moving to new export markets in Asia .

Figure 3: Export from Bangladesh (2004-2017)

Source: Author Constructed

With the cheaper rate and high quality of flower Bangladesh could have easily captured global market but for lack of promotion, foreign buyers are not aware of this low-cost export market. Bangladesh has not been even able to grab new import market. In order to make export move upward, Bangladesh will have to enter a new market, even though without government’s support it is not possible.

In the figure 05 it is shown that the export volume has been facing weakening growth since 2011 . In 2017 the export amount was \$.8 million which has marked the lowest export volume. In FY(2003-2004) the export was \$7,339,000.00 which quite impressive for beginning. Experts believe Bangladesh is not making any progress in flower export due to little promotion. The neighbour country India has been showing remarkable performance in export nevertheless it started exporting flowers for 2 decayed only. Even after having favourable climate and low labour cost, Bangladesh is not making any development and unable to compete its Asian counterparties.

Figure 4: Trendline and Growth analysis of Export from (2004-2022)

Source: Author-Constructed

Figure 5: Estimated values of Export (2017-2022)

Source: Author-Constructed

In the global market, the situation of flower export has completely altered as dominating countries are facing loss and production in those countries has also fallen. The market is going to the hand of developing markets and Asia. Bangladesh can easily capture this opportunity. The anticipation can be proven wrong if, only if domestic market understand the movement of the global trading and offer best from their part.

Opportunities:

1. If the government, private organization come forward and aid in developing the industry Bangladesh can penetrate the global market
2. Bangladesh is bestowed by natural climate and soil. Therefore, the flower can be produced more effectively than other European countries
3. Bangladesh has the advantage of low-cost labour. And the production cost is comparatively less than that of other countries. Bangladesh can provide the consumers lowest priced product with higher quality
4. The temper and durability of flowers of Bangladesh are high is started which can be the competitive advantage or flowers industry.
5. Bangladesh can replicate any flower in very short time. Like lily which was an import-dependent flower coming from India and Thailand. But Bangladesh has now started cultivating Lily locally.

Conclusion

The flower business is not only profitable but also sustaining in the long run. The study shows that flower production is more cost-effective than that of vegetables and other crops. The return on investment is almost double. Flowers are one of the key products in many countries that contribute to higher GDP. Flowers have significant economic values internationally. Different developing countries have flourished their economic condition by flower export. Many countries in Europe and South Africa are now leading in the global market by the mean of flower business. The world flower industry is now changing, and the exporters are losing their position. Global Buyers are looking for markets from where they can purchase flowers in c cheaper rate. This shift in the global demand has caused many emerging countries overtake the leading position. Many countries in Asia are also trying to take the opportunity. In the past Asian countries used to export flowers only to the neighbouring countries. However, this situation does not exist anymore. European countries are importing from Asia and Africa.

Bangladesh has a very favourable climate to turn the flower business into booming industry. Bangladesh has the competitive advantage of low-cost labour which many European countries lack. Therefore, Bangladesh can also catch the global flower market by exporting flower at a

lower price. With earning foreign currency, flower business can play vital role in employment generation and poverty reduction. AT present 19 zillas are occupied in flower farming. Most of the farmers are satisfied with flower business yet exporters and retailers are not highly delighted with the current condition of flower business. Despite having potentiality, the export has been dropped for the last few years. This was caused by many reasons primality for the poor quality, political unrest, little promotion, lack of ad from government etc. Exporters considered Bangladesh as an emerging flower market which has the prospects of being one of the top exporters.

The study shows that if the impeding factors are eliminated, Bangladesh can achieve a significant position in the global flower industry. The domestic market is drowned by some challenges such as weak research activities, unorganised market, lack of post-harvest management, dependency on import, little knowledge of farmers, underdeveloped machineries, lack of cold value chain and air-conditioned vehicles, lack of promotion, high priced airlines fare, no permanent market etc. Government's initiative is also very limited. The government should be active and these problems should be solved by taking appropriate actions for the proper growth of flower business in the domestic as well as international market.

Limitations of the Study

In spite of achieving all objectives, a few limitations were addressed throughout this study. The limitations of the study are as follows:

1. Very few Research has been done on this given topic
2. Updated information is not available regarding flower business and floriculture.
3. The difficulty of getting information from respondents.
4. Books, articles, journals are not updated.
5. Lack of time to reach the consumer personally to make them understand the question.
6. Lack of information on the websites
7. The unwillingness of the respondents to provide required information
8. Difficulties in communicating with some respondents, as they have little understanding of the topic of the research.

Future Areas of Improvement

Bangladesh has potential in flower business as it is blessed with natural resources like fertile soil, favourable climate and other stimulating topologies. The paper has examined various factors of flower potentiality of Bangladesh and considered following actions will improve the current situation.

1. Supplying modern flower packaging materials can extend the longevity of flowers. Non-perishable flower packaging system could help the flower growers to add more value to flowers.
2. In foreign countries, the production is dependent on greenhouse but Bangladesh has some natural advantage over those countries. But for producing sensitive flowers greenhouse is required.
3. Collaboration with an international organisation as ITC, WTO and USAID will help to promote Bangladesh in the world market.
4. Participation in the international fair, workshop, the seminar can promote Bangladesh' flower industry to the world.
5. Participants related to flower business (farmers, wholesalers, retailers) should provide proper knowledge about scientific cultivation, advanced pest and fertilizer, developed marketing strategy and preservation, packaging, and distribution. Development in research and development sector for flower production and storage should also be initiated
6. Farmers are required to provide skill development training on Post Harvest Management of flowers.
7. Establishment of cold chain is indispensable for maintaining the quality of flower. Therefore, concerned authority should develop cold chain system for flowers' preservation.
8. Establishing permanent flower wholesale market is mandatory. City corporations, municipal authorities and district administrators could establish permanent wholesale and retail flower market.
9. The airline should reduce fare price of containers. The airline authority should also consider allowing more space for flower export

10. The government should facilitate this sector, as flower industry is as lucrative as other major exporting industries in Bangladesh. The government should allow 20% subsidy in the sector.

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